

Isolation and Identification of L-Leucine as DNP-L-Leucine Hydrochloride in the Leaves of *Garcinia indica*

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L-Leucine has been isolated by conversion to DNP hydrochloride from the young leaves of *Garcinia indica* Chois. (N.O. Guttiferae).

Garcinia indica, a medium sized tree grows wild in the forests of Western Ghats of India. Various parts of the plant are used in the Indian system of medicine for a number of ailments. The seeds yield a valuable fat known in commerce as "Kokum butter" and is suitable for some pharmaceutical preparations.^{1,2} This investigation was undertaken since very little work of the type is reported in literature on this tree.

The shade dried powdered leaves (100 gms) were extracted with rectified spirit and the extract after concentration at 40°–50° under reduced pressure was well triturated with 20 ml of water which dissolved the free amino acids. The colouring matter was removed by extraction with chloroform. The TLC of water extract after concentration showed the presence of free amino acids and phosphotidylethanolamine by spraying with ninhydrin reagent.³ Inactivated silica gel G plates were used in phenol : water (80 : 20, v/v) as developing solvent.

The free amino acids present in the aqueous extract were converted into DNP hydrochloride derivatives⁴ yielding yellow crystals which on purification⁵ had m.p. 105°–106°. The identity of this product was confirmed as DNP-L-Leucine hydrochloride by T.L.C. on activated silica gel G plates against an authentic sample using N-butanol : 25% ammonia (4 : 1, v/v)⁶ as developing solvent (N, found 72.96%, required 72.61%).

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